

Robust Discrete Controller Design For An Unmanned Research Vehicle (URV) Using Discrete Quantitative Feedback Theory

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Abstract

The application of non-minimum phase (nmp) w' -plane discrete MIMO (multiple-input-multiple-output) Quantitative Feedback Theory (QFT) to the design of a three-axis rate-commanded automatic flight control system for a URV is presented. The URV model used is a seven input three output state-space system derived from the small-angle perturbation equations of motion. Plant parameter uncertainty consists of six flight conditions derived from variations in the aircraft center of gravity, airspeed, and gross weight. A weighting matrix Δ is used to post-multiply the plants for blending the seven effector inputs into three *effective* rate-command inputs and resulting in an *effective* plant $P_e = P\Delta$. Second order effector models and first order feedback sensor models are included in the plant. A time-scaled recursive algorithm is used to transform the continuous plant models to the w' -plane thereby avoiding the numeric problems associated with an intermediate z -plane representation. All continuous URV plant elements are minimum phase (mp). The discrete-plane transformation, however, produces a *sampling* nmp zero and one other nmp zero due to the three pole excess actuator/sensor model elements. These nmp elements limit the available loop bandwidth ($l_i(j\omega)$). Standard QFT design is used, with plant templates $\mathcal{P} = \{P(j\omega)\}$ which quantitatively express the plant uncertainty. Due to the loop bandwidth limitations, only stability bounds are derived. The loop transmissions ($l_i(j\omega)$) are then shaped to achieve the maximum levels subject to the stability bounds. This is followed in the usual QFT manner with design of the prefilters. The design performance verification results are hybrid (amplitude limiting) simulations up to and including limiting of all surfaces. Some flight conditions are open-loop unstable so, in these cases, limiting induces instability. In this design, instability results only when all surfaces are at or very close to limiting. Hard limiting and nominal performance is shown.

Background

The Lambda URV, owned and operated by the Flight Dynamics Directorate (WL/FIGL) at Wright-Patterson AFB, OH, is a research vehicle used to subject flight control system components and control algorithms to the rigors of actual flight. It is a small mono-wing pusher propeller driven aircraft with a 14 foot wing span. It sports a conventional control surface

configuration with ailerons and flaps on the main wing and elevators and rudder on a conventional tail. Presently the pilot directly manipulates the seven control surfaces (effectors) individually to attain the desired vehicle response. This study will enhance Lambda's utility by designing an implementable noninteracting rate-commanded automatic flight control system. The controllers and prefilters resulting from this study will be flight tested on Lambda.

This design study is part of a wider ranging philosophy at the Air Force Institute of Technology (AFIT) to investigate and develop any and all possible flight control system design methods and theory. QFT is one of the design techniques receiving attention at AFIT and has been applied quite successfully to many different aircraft and design scenarios. It is used in this study as part of that wide ranging philosophy, and this paper describes the discrete QFT design of an automatic flight control system for Lambda. A detailed description of all aspects of this design and the aircraft data used is contained in [11]. MIMO QFT is found in references [3, 7, 4, 6, 5, 8, 1, 9].

Aircraft Model

Linearized perturbation equations of motion are derived from the aerodynamic stability and control derivative data generated by the Digital DATCOM CAD package used to design Lambda. The standard state space form is used:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{\mathbf{x}}(t) &= \mathbf{A} \mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{B} \mathbf{u}(t) \\ \mathbf{y}(t) &= \mathbf{C} \mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{D} \mathbf{u}(t)\end{aligned}$$

with conventional aircraft longitudinal and lateral system perturbation states $\mathbf{x}(t)$ of θ , u , α , q , ϕ , β , p and r and effector inputs $\mathbf{u}(t)$ of δ_{eL} , δ_{eR} , δ_{fL} , δ_{fR} , δ_{aL} , δ_{aR} and δ_r . The effector inputs (δ) are in units of radians and each effector is independently controllable. The system states are in units of radians and radians/second except for perturbed forward speed u in feet/second. The controlled outputs are $\mathbf{y}(t) = [q(t) \ p(t) \ r(t)]^T$ (pitch-rate, roll-rate, and yaw-rate respectively).

QFT design uses the *a priori* bounded range of plant parameter variation to shape unity feedback loop transmissions such that the *a priori* specified system performance specifications are met. Robustness is built into the design through the use of plant templates which quantitatively express the bounded plant variation. Six level flight conditions provide the plant

variation for this design. Table 1 shows the important elements of each flight condition used. Flight condition 5 and 6

Table 1: The Aircraft Flight Conditions

Plant #	Spd (kts)	CG (% MAC)	Wt (lbs)	α (AOA)
1	40	50	150	10.4°
2	100	50	150	-1.64°
3	100	25	200	-0.96°
4	70	50	200	1.9°
5	70	25	150	0.556°
6 ‡	70	25	150	0.556°

appear to be the same (‡), however the stability derivatives are different in those cases.

The seven effectors are used by blending them to form an *effective* three input system plant P_e for each of the six level flight conditions. A weighting matrix Δ is used such that $P_e = P\Delta$. Elements of Δ are selected so that the "natural" effectors for a given output are weighted more heavily and so that $|P_e(s)|$ is minimum phase (mp). Optimality in weighting matrix selection is not considered in this design.

Seven identical second order effector actuator models ($324/s^2 + 25.4s + 324$) for each of the seven effectors and three identical first order rate sensor models ($50/s + 50$) for the three-axis rate sensor feedback gyro signals are included in P_e such that:

$$P_e(s) = P(s)\Delta \begin{bmatrix} 324 \\ s^2 + 25.4s + 324 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 50 \\ s + 50 \end{bmatrix}$$

The system models provided for Lambda for the six flight conditions are longitudinally (1x1) and laterally (2x2) decoupled.

Discrete QFT

Discrete QFT design is accomplished readily in the w' -plane when $w' \approx s$ for the frequency band of concern and thus takes full advantage of the well-developed s -plane QFT design methods. The six plants are transformed to the w' -plane with a time-scaled recursive algorithm [2]. Data hold assumptions are used so that for each plant case:

$$P_e(s) \Rightarrow \boxed{\text{Hofmann Algorithm}} \Rightarrow [G_{ZOH}P_e](w')$$

A 60 Hz sample rate is used.

The Lambda MIMO sampled-data QFT system is a pre-filtered (F) unity feedback cascade compensated (G) system [11, Fig 3.2] with sampled control inputs and sampled input and output controller signals. For this configuration, transformed to the w' -plane, the Lambda MIMO system is expressible as:

$$T(w') = [I + [G_{ZOH}P_e](w')G(w')]^{-1} \bullet [G_{ZOH}P_e](w')G(w')F(w') \quad (1)$$

The controller matrix $G(w')$ and the prefilter matrix $F(w')$ are design variables, however, the above MIMO formulation

of control ratios is not practical for design. Rather, a MISO (multiple-input-single-output) equivalent formulation of the MIMO system is used [4, 1, 11]. Separate "channel" design problems result from that formulation of the MIMO system since interchannel responses in the MIMO system are equivalently expressed as disturbances to the MISO equivalent channels.

The MISO form is derived from (1) with $G_{ZOH}P_e = P_{zo}$ as follows [4]:

$$T = [I + P_{zo}G]^{-1} P_{zo}GF$$

For a nonsingular P_{zo} :

$$\begin{aligned} [I + P_{zo}G] T &= P_{zo}GF \\ [P_{zo}^{-1} + G] T &= GF \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

P_{zo}^{-1} is partitioned so that:

$$P_{zo}^{-1} = \Lambda + B_p \quad (3)$$

where

$$\Lambda = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{q_{1,1}} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{q_{2,2}} & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \frac{1}{q_{i,i}} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B_p = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{1}{q_{1,2}} & \dots & \frac{1}{q_{1,i}} \\ \frac{1}{q_{2,1}} & 0 & \dots & \frac{1}{q_{2,i}} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{1}{q_{i,1}} & \frac{1}{q_{i,2}} & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

(3) is substituted into (2) to form the MISO equivalent system:

$$T = [\Lambda + G]^{-1} [GF - B_pT] \quad (4)$$

$Q(w')$ is the MISO equivalent form of the plant P_e and its elements $q_{i,j}$ are related to the plant such that $q_{i,j}(w') = 1/p_{i,j}^*(w')$ where the $p_{i,j}^*(w')$'s are the elements of P_{zo}^{-1} .

Fully expanded, T from (4) above is a matrix whose elements represent the MISO equivalent loops of the original MIMO system [11, pp 3-15,16]. The factor $g_{i,i}/(1 + g_{i,i})$ appears in each element of row i in T . Thus, $g_{i,i}$ is synthesized to attenuate the coupling disturbances and attain the tracking performance for the elements of row i of T . $g_{i,i}$ is synthesized to ensure that the frequency plane specifications derived from the response model for a given MISO channel are met or exceeded by the channel loop transmission. $f_{i,i}$ is synthesized to position the loop transmission magnitude properly for specified tracking performance. Three separate single-loop equivalent design synthesis problems result from the MISO equivalent URV system as opposed to the nine interrelated design problems represented by the MIMO system in (1).

Two conditions are required for application of QFT to a MIMO system and its MISO equivalent form. First and most obvious, P_e^{-1} must exist. Second, *diagonal dominance* must exist [4]. For the 2x2 case, *diagonal dominance* exists if:

$$|p_{1,1}p_{2,2}| \geq |p_{1,2}p_{2,1}| \quad \text{as } \omega \Rightarrow \infty$$

where $p_{i,j}$ are elements of a 2x2 plant matrix P_e .

The discrete MISO equivalent plant elements $g_{i,j}(w')$ are formed and standard QFT templates constructed, however, only stability bounds are derived for the subsequent channel loop shaping. The transformation to the w' -plane produces at least one nmp sampling zero. Other nmp zeros can occur if the continuous system is nmp or the plants have many excess poles. The Lambda plants $P_e(s)$ are all mp, however, the plant elements all have a four pole excess due primarily to the three pole effector actuator/sensor models. Two nmp zeros result in the $g_{i,j}(w')$'s for Lambda. These nmp zeros introduce the phase lag that limits the maximum achievable loop transmission in a discrete design. Thus, it is usually much easier and more productive to construct only stability bounds and synthesize the maximum loop transmission possible subject to these stability bounds.

Stability bounds are constructed on the Nichols chart by specifying a phase margin requirement and a nominal plant g_o as a reference. A 45° phase margin is used for Lambda. This corresponds to the $3dB$ M contour on the Nichols chart. Since the disturbance response is very sensitive to changes in ζ , it is further required that the 45° phase margin be extended for a range of frequencies v_k ($w' = u + jv$). Plant templates are used to extend the phase margin or stability bound for v_k by constructing a loci of the nominal plant points as the v_k plant template is moved around the M contour so that no part of the template penetrates the contour. The nominal loop transmission l_o is then shaped so that these boundaries are not penetrated.

The Lambda design results in three separate MISO loop design problems where $l_i = g_i q_{i,i}$ ($i = 1, 2, 3$ pitch, roll, yaw). For a particular loop i , the nominal loop transmission is $l_o = g_i q_o$. l_o is then shaped as desired and g_i is derived by dividing l_o by the plant ($g_i = l_o/q_o$). This is fine if the order of g_i is not a concern and q_o is stable and mp. The phase contribution of unstable elements of q_o are easily accounted for by including them in the loop shaping. By the same token, nmp elements of q_o are included in l_o to ensure that their phase contribution is also accounted for. Since lowest-order compensation is a concern for Lambda, l_o is shaped by including all elements of q_o so that elements of g_i are selected directly during shaping.

These separate MISO designs involve some overdesign due to the fact that the MISO equivalent equations are developed with *worst case* channel disturbance input assumptions. The overdesign is reduced by applying the improved QFT design method [5]. This improved method makes use of the correlation that exists between the MISO equivalent loops. Loop shaping and selection of g_i constitutes *knowledge* gained for a particular MISO channel. Due to the channel correlation, this *knowledge* is available to further refine the disturbance contributions to the other MISO channels. Incorporating this *knowledge* in subsequent loop designs reduces the *worst case* disturbance input assumptions thereby reducing the overdesign associated with the original MISO formulation.

The improved method is used on Lambda's lateral 2×2 system. The smallest bandwidth loop is designed first with the original MISO equations. The g_i of this loop is then inserted into the loop two modified MISO equations thereby incorporating the loop one *knowledge* for the second loop shaping. The 2×2 modified design equations are given below without derivation. The subscripts on the elements of these equations

denote the order of loop synthesis. 1 is the first loop synthesized, 2 the second, etc.

$$l_{2e} = g_{2e} q_{2,2e} = \frac{g_{2e} q_{2,2}(1 + g_{1e} q_{1,1})}{1 - \gamma_{1,2} + g_{1e} q_{1,1}}$$

$$\gamma_{1,2} = \frac{P_{1,2} P_{2,1}}{P_{1,1} P_{2,2}}$$

$q_{2,2e}$ is the notation used to denote the effective design transfer function of loop two modified by the known g_1 .

Channel prefilter design ($f_{i,i}$) is accomplished in the usual manner as described in [1, 11, 4]. After all g_i and $f_{i,i}$ channel elements are designed, they are transformed to the z -plane by the Tustin transformation and expressed as difference equations for implementation in the Lambda flight control computer.

Design

The r -loop (yaw-rate) design in the lateral Lambda system is described below. It is the first loop designed of the lateral system. Improved QFT is applied to the p -loop (roll-rate), the second loop synthesized in the lateral system. Since the lateral and longitudinal aircraft modes are completely decoupled, q -loop (pitch-rate) is a SISO (single-input-single-output) system without lateral channel disturbances. Once the templates are generated and the nominal plant selected, the loop designs are all very similar and are all presented in detail in [11].

A minimum degree-of-freedom design is desired and thus diagonal G and F are used. Nondiagonal G and/or F can be used when more degrees-of-freedom are needed to meet performance specifications. Also, a noninteracting rate-commanded system is specified for Lambda so that:

$$T(w') \approx \begin{bmatrix} \frac{q(w')}{q_{cmd}(w')} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{p(w')}{p_{cmd}(w')} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{r(w')}{r_{cmd}(w')} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Time-domain response models to specify the desired closed-loop system performance are synthesized for the elements of (5). The figures-of-merit for the r -loop are listed in Table 2. The response model data for all loops including the transfer functions used are found in [11, Appen D]. The w' -plane fre-

Table 2: Figures-of-Merit for the w' -plane QFT Response Models

Model	T_r (sec)	T_s (sec)	M_p $\frac{rad}{sec}$	FV $\frac{rad}{sec}$
$\frac{r_{LB}(w')}{r_{cmdLB}(w')}$	3.48	6.22	1.0	1.0
$\frac{r_{UB}(w')}{r_{cmdUB}(w')}$	1.76	3.13	1.0	1.0

quency bounds resulting from these models are shown in [11, Appen D] and in Figures 3 and 4 as B_l and B_u .

Plant templates are constructed for the r -loop and are shown in Figure 1. Plant case 1 is selected as the nominal plant for the loop shaping. The subscripts in the equations below denote the original system output order and not the

Figure 1: Yaw-Rate Channel Plant Templates ($q_{3,3}$) $v_t = 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 0.3, 1, 1.4, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 10, 50, 100, 1000, 10000$ rad/sec With Plant Case # 1 Nominal

order of loop synthesis. The nominal loop transmission is:

$$l_{o_3}(w') = g_3(w') q_{o_3,3}(w')$$

$$q_{o_3,3}(w') = \frac{1.29993e-4 (-0.066135)(120)(-140.0997)(155.5963)}{(-0.4265 \pm j1.4601)(-12.8472 \pm j12.6911)} \cdot \frac{(-935.7121)}{(-47.3705)} \quad (6)$$

Only the roots and gain of $q_{o_3,3}$ are shown in (6). A negative root denotes a left-half plane (lhp) pole or zero. Shaping of l_{o_3} to meet or exceed the stability bounds ensures that all plant cases modeled, along with the unmodeled cases contained within the plant templates, also meet or exceed the stability bounds and ensures a minimum phase margin of 45° is attained. During shaping, consideration is also given to synthesis of the maximum allowable loop gain. All loops are synthesized as Type 1 for zero steady-state error to a step input. This requires that g_3 have a pole at the origin. Figure 2 shows the constraining bounds on the initial l_{o_3} for $g_3(w') = 1/w'$ and the final l_{o_3} for:

$$g_3(w') = \frac{223(w' + 0.3)(w' + 4.5)(w'^2 + 20w' + 324)}{w'(w' + 0.009)(w'^2 + 500w' + 250000)}$$

After nominal loop shaping, the prefilter is designed by forming and plotting the unfiltered closed-loop channel frequency responses $l_3^i/(1 + l_3^i)$ where $i = 1 - 6$ and $l_3^i = g_3 q_{3,3}$ corresponding to the six plant cases. The frequency response of the r -loop response models are also plotted to aid in selecting a prefilter which properly positions the loop transmissions in the frequency plane to meet r -loop tracking performance bounds (see Figure 3). The $f_{3,3}$ synthesized to meet the per-

Figure 2: Initial and Final l_{o_3} With Bounds

formance bounds is (see the filtered channel responses in Figure 4):

$$f_{3,3}(w') = \frac{0.004(w' + 200)}{w' + 0.8}$$

The design is verified by generating the time response of the channel for all plant cases.

$$r^i(w') = \frac{f_{3,3}(w') l_3^i(w')}{1 + l_3^i(w')} \Rightarrow r^i(t)$$

These are shown with the response model bounds in Figure 5.

The r -loop transmission is sufficient to meet the tracking and disturbance bounds had they been constructed. This is

Figure 3: Unfiltered Yaw-Rate Loop Transmissions $l_3^i/(1 + l_3^i)$

Figure 4: Filtered Yaw-Rate Loop Transmissions $f_{3,3}^i/(1+l_3^i)$

Figure 5: Yaw-Rate Channel Time Responses $r^i(t)$ $i = 1 - 6$ With Bounds

not the case, however, with the q and p loops. In those cases, low frequency uncertainty (see [11, Appen E]) is very large unlike the r -loop (see Fig 1). Tracking bounds at these frequencies are extremely high on the Nichols chart since the allowable variation in magnitude derived from the response models at these frequencies is very small. The nmp elements of those loops limit the maximum loop transmission and thus make it impossible to achieve enough gain and meet the low frequency tracking bounds. This situation results in sagging time responses in those channels which, for all practical purposes, may be unnoticeable to the Lambda pilot.

Simulation and Results

Each of the MISO channel designs are simulated as in Figure 5 to verify proper execution of the design synthesis. Hybrid MIMO system simulations are performed with Matrixx₁₀ to verify the complete MIMO system performance. The prefilter $F(z)$ and the controller $G(z)$ are implemented in discrete-time blocks and drive the continuous linear perturbation plant $P_c^i(s)$. A zero-order-hold device is incorporated between the controller output and the plant input. The actual amplitude limits on Lambda are used in the simulation to limit the deflection of the effectors. Effector actuator rate limits are not specified for Lambda's actuators and are thus not used in the simulation. Block diagrams of the simulation setup are found in [11].

A moderate and realistic $45^\circ/\text{sec}$, one second duration rate input is applied to each channel of the design individually. The longitudinal input does not affect the lateral channels and vice

versa due to the decoupling in the model so only the q response to a q_{cmd} input is shown for the longitudinal simulations. In contrast, the lateral system (2×2) is highly coupled. In the uncompensated $P(s)$, ailerons can produce nearly as much r response as the rudder and the rudder can produce nearly as much p response as the ailerons. For the lateral simulations, r and p responses are shown for r_{cmd} and p_{cmd} channel inputs. Note that the numbers in the following plots denote plant cases and only the more interesting plant cases are labeled.

Figure 6: q Responses For Plants 1-6 to a 1 sec Duration $45^\circ/\text{sec}$ Pitch-Rate (q) Input

Figure 7: p Responses For Plants 1-6 to a 1 sec Duration $45^\circ/\text{sec}$ Roll-Rate (p) Input

The responses in Figures 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 serve to demonstrate the success of the design. The effects of control surface limiting are evident on the plots where performance departs from specification. For example, plant case 1 in Figure 6 exhibits an appropriate response to the q_{cmd} input up to about 5 seconds where it begins to exhibit an oscillatory but stable response.

Figures 8 and 9 demonstrate the disturbance rejection attained by the design in the lateral system. Again here as with the longitudinal channel, the departure from specification occurs as all effectors reach deflection limits. Notice that substantial yaw can be commanded with no effector limiting. Bear in mind that maintenance of a 45° pitch-up command or a level 45° non-turning bank angle for an extended period of time as shown in the plots is not necessarily realistic for this type of aircraft. Also bear in mind that the models used for this design are valid for small-angle perturbations about the nominal level flight conditions. A $45^\circ/\text{sec}$ rate command is not a *small-angle* command.

A $500^\circ/\text{sec}$ rate input is applied to the individual channels of the design. This level of input will not be used on Lambda,

Figure 8: r Responses For Plants 1-6 to a 1 sec Duration $45^\circ/\text{sec}$ Roll-Rate (p) Input

Figure 9: p Responses For Plants 1-6 to a 1 sec Duration $45^\circ/\text{sec}$ Yaw-Rate (r) Input

Figure 10: r Responses For Plants 1-6 to a 1 sec Duration $45^\circ/\text{sec}$ Yaw-Rate (r) Input

Figure 11: q Responses For Plants 1-6 to a 1 sec Duration $500^\circ/\text{sec}$ Pitch-Rate (q) Input

however, for simulation purposes, it is necessary to investigate the system response in the nonlinear case when all effectors are quickly driven to limits. In these simulations, the effectors are driven to amplitude limits within 1 second.

The results derived from these simulations are shown in Table 3. Plots of all state variables and effectors are found in [11].

Table 3: Unstable Flight Conditions When All Effectors Are Fully Amplitude Limited

Configuration	Channel		
	q	p	r
Open-Loop $Q(w')$	2,4	2	none
Closed-Loop $45^\circ/\text{sec}$	none	1	none
Closed-Loop $500^\circ/\text{sec}$	4	1	none

Plants corresponding to flight conditions 2 and 4 are open-loop unstable in the q channel, but, instability in the closed-loop q channel only occurs for Plant 4 and only when the effectors are forced to hard limit with a large command input. Plant 2 is open-loop unstable in the p channel, however, Plant 1 is closed-loop unstable in the p channel for both simulations shown. Plant 1 is a minimum controllable flight condition and thus large effector deflections are needed to produce the desired responses. For the p channel, the effectors for Plant 1 limit quickly and induce the instability. The flight conditions are all stable in the r channel even with hard rudder limiting.

Generally, a control system with effectors operating at limits will respond nearly as it would in open-loop operation. Table 3 shows that the q channel performs better than that, the r channel performs as expected, and in the p channel there is a kind of tradeoff. In this case, plant 2 is open-loop unstable and closed-loop stable, but Plant 1 is open-loop stable and closed-loop unstable. Note that in any case instability occurs only when all effectors reach amplitude limits. Again bear in mind that the nonlinear operation of limiting is never addressed in the design synthesis although QFT techniques do exist for this. A linear feedback system design is accomplished and demonstrates the very beneficial nature and power of feedback.

Some extended (60 sec) coordinated turn simulations found in [11] add more credibility to the design. The steep bank turns (45°) are accomplished with no effector limiting and no instability. Further, a successful wing leveler autopilot function is designed and added to the new Lambda rate-command system design. It's design and simulation is found in [11, Chap 6].

Summary

The controllers and prefilters designed provide a three-axis noninteracting rate-commanded automatic flight control law implementation on the Lambda URV. The control laws are directly implementable and will be flight tested in the near future.

The effective plants $P_e^i(s)$, with a three pole actuator/sensor model, have an excess of four poles. This produces two nmp zeros in $[P_e^i(w')]$. The phase of these nmp zeros is accounted for by including them in the template generation and in the

Figure 12: p Responses For Plants 1-6 to a 1 sec Duration $500^\circ/\text{sec}$ Roll-Rate (p) Input

Figure 13: r Responses For Plants 1-6 to a 1 sec Duration $500^\circ/\text{sec}$ Roll-Rate (p) Input

Figure 14: p Responses For Plants 1-6 to a 1 sec Duration $500^\circ/\text{sec}$ Yaw-Rate (r) Input

Figure 15: r Responses For Plants 1-6 to a 1 sec Duration $500^\circ/\text{sec}$ Yaw-Rate (r) Input

nominal loop transmission shaping for each MISO channel. In this way, these nmp characteristics are handled *directly* and successful loop transmissions are synthesized for each MISO channel.

Hybrid nonlinear (effector amplitude limited) simulations on Matrixx of the completed design verify the successful application of discrete QFT. The yaw-rate channel meets all specifications. Due to the large uncertainty at low frequencies in the pitch-rate and roll-rate MISO channels, some low frequency tracking bounds are quite high and are not met by the respective loop transmissions. In a strict sense, *a priori* performance specifications are not met by the pitch-rate and roll-rate channels since the low frequency tracking bound violations result in minor sagging of the time responses. It is reasonable to assert that this may not be very noticeable or even detectable to the Lambda pilot. Pilots tend to rate aircraft on transient performance, and so, in that sense, the QFT designs generated in this study meet all specifications.

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